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Full-Scale Pilot Implementation for Car Sharing

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About GreenCharge

GreenCharge takes us a few important steps closer to achieving one of the dreams of modern cities: a zero-emission transport system based on electric vehicles running on green energy, with traffic jams and parking problems becoming things of the past. The project promotes:

Power to the people! The GreenCharge dream can only be achieved if people feel confident that they can access charging infrastructure as and when they need it. So GreenCharge is developing a smart charging system that lets people book charging in advance, so that they can easily access the power they need.

The delicate balance of power If lots of people try to charge their vehicles around the same time (e.g., on returning home from work), public electricity suppliers may struggle to cope with the peaks in demand. So, we are developing software for automatic energy management in local areas to balance demand with available supplies. This balancing act combines public supplies and locally produced reusable energy, using local storage as a buffer and staggering the times at which vehicles get charged.

Getting the financial incentives right Electric motors may make the wheels go round, but money makes the world go round. So we are devising and testing business models that encourage use of electric vehicles and sharing of energy resources, allowing all those involved to cooperate in an economically viable way.

Showing how it works in practice GreenCharge is testing all of these innovations in practical trials in Barcelona, Bremen and Oslo. Together, these trials cover a wide variety of factors: *vehicle type* (scooters, cars, buses), *ownership model* (private, shared individual use, public transport), *charging locations* (private residences, workplaces, public spaces, transport hubs), *energy management* (using solar power, load balancing at one charging station or within a neighbourhood, battery swapping), and *charging support* (booking, priority charging).

To help cities and municipalities make the transition to zero emission/sustainable mobility, the project is producing three main sets of results: (1) *innovative business models*; (2) *technological support*; and (3) *guidelines* for cost efficient and successful deployment and operation of charging infrastructure for Electric Vehicles (EVs).

The *innovative business models* are inspired by ideas from the sharing economy, meaning they will show how to use and share the excess capacity of private renewable energy sources (RES), private charging facilities and the batteries of parked EVs in ways that benefit all involved, financially and otherwise.

The *technological support* will coordinate the power demand of charging with other local demand and local RES, leveraging load flexibility and storage capacity of local stationary batteries and parked EVs. It will also provide user friendly charge planning, booking and billing services for EV users. This will reduce the need for grid investments, address range/charge anxiety and enable sharing of already existing charging facilities for EV fleets.

The *guidelines* will integrate the experience from the trials and simulations and provide advice on localisation of charging points, grid investment reductions, and policy and public communication measures for accelerating uptake of electromobility.

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable is dealing with the Full-Scale Pilot implementation in Bremen and involves the two demonstrators:

- GreenCharge@work demonstrator BRE.D1 (run by PMC)
- eCar Sharing demonstrator BRE.D2 (run by ZET).

Whereas in D2.11 *Pilot Component and Preparation for Full-Scale Pilot (Bremen)* the applied components of these 2 demonstrators are described, in the presented deliverable the installation and configuration of the involved components are described in detail.

In the BRE.D1 demonstrator, the hardware system includes PV solar panels, inverters, and a 2nd-life buffer battery system. During the demonstration preparation, setting up the hardware system and adaption of the proprietary backend have been delayed. Now, the innovative gridctrl charging infrastructure system allows the user to be guided within a whole set of charging stations. The current system (initial version v1.0) is able to:

- provide reliable charge services considering constraints due to local grid power limit
- aggregate charging session data
- collect research data.

Improved setups and developments of this key component for charging infrastructure (gridctrl) will be handled in a 2nd stage to provide with version v2.0 a fully operable demonstrator.

The BRE.D2 demonstrator is ready to collect the required research data. The previous CarSharing system had been replaced by a new system developed by ZET. This includes the replaced in-vehicle system, a new fleet management system, and an advanced CarSharing customer frontend (ZET App).

The new system is able to:

- Collect research data
- Provide innovative CarSharing Services to Customers
- Provide real-time information about public transport options to users of eCarSharing.

As of November 2019 – after a series of adjustments - a real-time dataflow test between all system components had been successfully implemented. Since then, the BRE.D2 demonstrator is fully operable and used in test runs.

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List of Abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAA	Authentication-Authorization-Accounting
App	Application
Auth	Authentication
BMI	Battery Management Interface
BMS	Battery Management System
CDR	Charge Detail Record
CMS	Charge Management System
CPO	ChargePoint Operator
EMP	E-Mobility Provider
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVSE	E-vehicle supply equipment
h/w and s/w	Hardware and Software
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NEMS	Neighbourhood Energy Management System
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
OTA Key	Hardware provided by OTA keys S.A. (Continental corporation)
POI	Point of Interest (in this case EVSE)
PV	PhotoVoltaics
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
SC	SCenario
SoC	State-of-Charge (battery)
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UC	Use Case

List of Definitions

Table 2: List of definitions

Definition	Explanation
Application Programming Interface	Application Programming Interface (API) is a set of clearly defined methods of communication among various components.
Demonstrator	Implements some measures to demonstrate the GreenCharge innovative solution to smart and green charging. A demonstrator consists of hardware and software installed on some specific site.
Description of Work (DoW)	Part of the formal “Grant Agreement” between the consortium and the funding authority, defining in detail the work to be carried out and the results to be produced.
Gateway	Joins two networks so the device on one network can communicate with the device on another network
Photovoltaic	Photovoltaic panels (solar cell panels) convert light into electricity using semiconducting materials
Scenario	A scenario describes a specific use of a proposed system by illustrating some interaction with the proposed system as viewed from the outside, e.g., by a user, using specific examples. In GreenCharge, a scenario is a higher level of description of the system and can be modelled using one or several use cases.
Use Case	A use case describes how a system will be used and is a tool for modelling requirements of a system. In GreenCharge, a scenario is a higher level of description of the system and can be modelled using one or several use cases.

1 About this Deliverable

1.1 Why would I want to read this deliverable?

This deliverable describes the implementation of the two demonstrators at the Bremen pilot, i.e. the solutions developed for charging at work and for car-sharing at BRE.D1 and BRE.D2, respectively. The deliverable gives an overview of hardware and software, new developments and the integration of the various components for the demonstrators. The report also contains descriptions of the installation and configuration of the demonstrators.

1.2 Intended readership/users

This deliverable is mainly targeting readers with technical knowledge regarding design and implementation of e-mobility and/or car-sharing solutions.

The GreenCharge project partners involved on design, development or deployment of pilots should read this deliverable in order to understand the current implementation and find potential cross-demo integrations for the next iteration step.

Other intended readers are external stakeholders planning to deploy e-mobility solutions with smart and green charging and also developers of car-sharing concepts and software for such solutions. Additional readers should be component providers that want to design components that fits the GreenCharge architecture.

1.3 Structure

The deliverable has a simple structure, reflecting the two different demonstration scenarios to be demonstrated in Bremen:

BRE.D1 – “GreenCharge@work” Charging occurs within a distributed network of charging stations, using preferably on-site RES connected to a buffer storage with used batteries. Priority-charging is enabled for a sub-group of EV-drivers, such as visitors and business fleet EVs.

BRE.D2 – “eCar-Sharing in a residential neighbourhood”. Station-based CarSharing featuring more convenient and smarter way of booking and charging of the shared EVs.

1.4 Other project deliverables that may be of interest

The following public project deliverables might be useful for the reader to get a more comprehensive view on the conditions and relationship of the Bremen pilot.

The hardware and software components presented in this document are based on inputs from the following deliverables:

- D2.9 Description of Bremen Pilot and User Needs - this document describes the Bremen pilot in terms of challenges, user needs, use cases, scenarios, stakeholders and locations to be involved and the baseline.

- D2.10 Implementation Plan for Bremen Pilot - this document describes the planning of the tests to be carried out at the pilot site. It includes scenarios to be demonstrated, time schedules, stakeholders and locations selected, users selected for workshops and for testing, hardware and software to be installed, tests to be run and data to be collected, etc.
- D2.14 – Intermodal On-street Car Sharing Stations in New Housing Development – this document describes the new generation intermodal car sharing station with electric charging.

The two other pilots have provided similar deliverables describing user needs, implementation plans and pilot components. The so-called “sister deliveries” are as follows:

- Oslo: D2.6 Full-Scale Pilot Implementation in Building Block - “Sister” delivery describing the integrated smart charging solution installed in the building block, prepared for balancing charging of EVs with local energy use and electricity production.
- Barcelona: D2.19 Full-Scale Pilot Implementation for Smart Charge and EV Fleet Management - “Sister” delivery describing the integrated smart charging solution installed, prepared for integrating battery swapping hub and shared office user charging points solution with smart planning, booking and billing solutions and balanced with local energy use and electricity production.

The adaptation and integration of the components presented in this document shall be compliant with the architecture and interoperability specification defined in the following deliverables:

- D4.1 – Initial Architecture Design and Interoperability Specification: this document describes the initial version of the GreenCharge architecture and the specification of interfaces and protocols for interoperability.
- D4.2 – Final Architecture Design and Interoperability Specification: this document describes the final version of the GreenCharge architecture and the specification of interfaces and protocols for interoperability. This is the refined version of architecture based on feedbacks and lessons learned from pilots and evaluations.

This deliverable describes the installation, configuration and deployment of the integrated prototype developed and described in the following deliverables:

- D4.3 Initial Version of Integrated Prototype – deliverable describing the initial version of the integrated prototype based on D4.1. Describing the software implementation and development in more detail.

2 Overview Bremen Pilot

Public eCar-Sharing and smart charging options provided for commuting employees are the core elements of the Bremen Pilot. As mentioned in D2.9 *Description of Bremen Pilot and User Needs*, providing Car-Sharing service had already proven promising effects in terms of reducing the number of car-owners within an urban environment. The implementation of electric vehicles in a car-sharing service might have a real “GreenCharge-effect” by reducing airborne pollutants from combustion engines. Therefore, the overall goal of the Bremen Pilot is an improvement of existing concepts, to offer user-friendly and sustainable options for individual mobility.

To fulfil its purpose, the Bremen Pilot examines two types of use cases:

- (a) business-related use cases with commuting employees, and
- (b) use cases relevant for public users.

The first case (a) addresses the increasing fraction of EVs that is expected to be part of the daily commuter traffic. Peak load on company sites caused by simultaneous charging demand can be handled best by smart charging solutions employing PV and stationary buffer batteries.

In the second case (b), persisting usage of a car in a private environment, e.g., residential neighbourhoods, is considered. Offering Car-Sharing services can lower the need for private car ownership. Moreover, private trips can be more sustainable, if electric vehicles are used for CarSharing service. However, eCar-Sharing service implies specific requirements for its operation in addition to a Car-Sharing service with combustion engine cars.

This section is an overview of the components used in the Bremen Pilot.

The Bremen pilot comprises the following two demonstrators:

- I. BRE.D1 – “GreenCharge@work”
- II. BRE.D2 – “eCar-Sharing in a residential neighborhood”.

To meet the requirements of both these demonstrators, hardware and software (backends, Apps, Aggregator) needed to be modified and installed. Each of the components of the demonstrators fulfills a function within the general GreenCharge Architecture scheme as has been presented in D4.1 *Initial Architecture Design*.

Figure 1: Overall GreenCharge Architecture (Source: D4.1)

The following table illustrates the components used within the Bremen pilot and describes how these components refer to the above GreenCharge Architecture.

Service	Component name	Description	Demo site	Type	Partner
Charge Service Provisioning	PMC App "GreenCharge"	React-based WebApp used by customers to book and remotely control a charging session	BRE.D1	SW	PMC
Charge Station Operation	gridctrl.ENCORE	charging infrastructure software platform providing user authentication and authorization management, charge-point monitoring, and data aggregation from energy meters	BRE.D1	SW	PMC
EV Charging	gridctrl.ENCORE		BRE.D1	SW	PMC
Local Energy Management	gridctrl.aggregator	autonomous network + energy gateway solution to connect on-site-components (e.g., charging points, energy meters, energy storage systems) to gridctrl.ENCORE backend via unified communication interface (single link)	BRE.D1	HW/SW	PMC
Roaming*)	Gridctrl.ENCORE with HUBJECT HBS	Roaming provided by Hubject HBS platform (external service)	BRE.D1	SW	PMC
Mobility as a Service	CS-Frontend (ZET APP)	The ZET App provides EV access as well as information about public transport to the customer	BRE.D2	SW	ZET
Fleet management	Fleet management system	This Backend system provides EV status information to the fleet manager	BRE.D2	SW	ZET
EV In-vehicle system	OTA Key Box	Vehicle system plugged to the EV OBD2. It allows the communication between EV and other s/w components	BRE.D2	HW	ZET
EV charging	Wall boxes	5 wall boxes enabling charging for CarSharing EVs at local housing blocks	BRE.D2	HW	ZET

*) not supported in this initial version

Table 3: Components overview of Bremen pilot

3 GreenCharge@work demonstrator BRE.D1

The BRE.D1 demonstrator showcases a smart and sustainable charging solution and is designed to tackle the following 2 use cases (see Appendix D2.9), which in turn build on 2 scenarios as described in the project DoW:

Use case UC#1: Booking Enforcement for priority charging

In some cases, EVs need charging immediately on arrival at the charging station (independent of their respective SoC). At a charging station owned (or just operated) by a company, this situation could apply, e.g., to company fleet EVs, VIP-owned cars, and (business) visitors. Access to any of the suitable charging points (not a specific parking spot) is to be arranged through pre-booking and should be possible via mobile app/web and at least until 1h before arrival.

Use case UC#2: Commuters charging at work using PV energy supply

Commuters have the chance to park & charge their EV (private or company-owned) on their employer's site via PV, and/or from electric energy buffered in a storage of used (2nd-life) automotive batteries. The PV energy supply and SoC of both the EV and the buffer battery have to be synchronized for the time of charging, i.e. during working hours. If this cannot be handled by the end of his/her individual workday (due to, e.g., low power), then the commuter should receive a notification on his/her smartphone. This would give the user enough time and opportunity to reconnect his/her EV to an alternate charging point (without PV).

To account for both use cases, the BRE.D1 demonstrator was originally devised as a set of 4 charging sites (CS#1...4) with different specifications that altogether can be managed using the proprietary "gridctrl" charging system. This system is provided by one of the local stakeholders and includes customized extensions made for the GreenCharge project.

The following 3 functional approaches were considered, when designing the charging systems in order to analyze different aspects of the charge@work use cases:

(1) One dedicated and customized technology prototype charging station (CS#3)

This station includes 2nd-life batteries, PV solar panels, and an advanced energy management system. This site has been completely re-engineered within the GreenCharge project to meet data acquisition needs.

(2) One derived technology prototype charging station (CS#1)

This station uses the same backend technology as CS#3, but neither includes a buffer battery storage nor PV capabilities (to be integrated into a building with optional PV extension). This station will be equipped with new components after the first prototype is ready to test the adaptability of the technology.

During set-up phase the location (Parkallee) had to be abandoned. The system, however, could be transferred to a new location close to CS#3. To avoid confusion, this new site is named CS#5 in the following.

CS#3 and CS#5, together with PV and stationary battery are forming the initial part of a multi-station smart charging environment.

(3) Two charging stations with off-the-shelf charging components (CS#2 + CS#4)

These stations are used just to compare with the customized prototypes, and also to provide reliable charging options in addition to the developed prototypes. They are capable to record a very limited dataset only (session data) and therefore cannot be used for detailed evaluations in the project. They were included as part of the demonstrator to provide reliable charging opportunities and securing a positive user experience.

Figure 2: Overview of customized (left) and off-the-shelf (right) components

These 4 charging stations were chosen to be in close spatial proximity within the Bremen University campus.

Figure 3: Relocation of charger within demonstrator BRE.D1

Comment: To avoid any confusion, the relocated “CS#01” will be renamed “CS#05” in the following chapters.

3.1 Overall architecture and components involved

The following figure shows the top-level architecture of the demonstrator BRE.D1 including all charging stations, their inter-connections, and the overall management system. Each station/system is connected via a dedicated link (public internet) to the “gridctrl” cloud system, which aggregates the evaluation data, manages the charging points, and provides basic system monitoring capability.

Figure 4: Architecture of the demonstrator BRE.D1 (GreenCharge@work)

In the GreenCharge@work demo the following core components are involved. The status and results from the tests of each component to be integrated are given in the following [Table 4](#).

Component	Site	Type	Comment
ZEBRA Battery System	CS#3	h/w	2 (out of 5) batteries removed from EVs are fully operational
PV Inverters	CS#3	h/w	tested and fully operational
PV Panels	CS#3	h/w	tested and found to be in good condition
Battery Inverters	CS#3	h/w	tested individually; not tested as part of the storage system
Battery Chargers	CS#3	h/w	new chargers to be installed
Smart Meters	CS#3	h/w	tested and fully operational
Charge Controllers	CS#2,3	h/w	new charge socket controllers installed and tested (fully operational)
Wallboxes (prototype)	CS#3	h/w	installed and tested (fully operational)
DC Charger	CS#4	h/w	operational, but unable to record all of the required datasets
Charging Station (residential student home)	CS#2	h/w	operational, but unable to record all of the required datasets
Charging Station (parking garage)	CS#1 (CS#5)	h/w	uses the same charging outlets as CS#3; installation still pending
gridctrl.aggregator	ALL	h/w s/w	initial version has been deployed to CS#3; development version still in use
gridctrl.ENCORE	ALL	s/w	development version still in use
Data Storage System	ALL	s/w	SQL-based, distributed data storage system in operation (MariaDB)

Table 4: Components involved in the demonstrator BRE.D1

3.2 Adaptations done for the Charge@Work demonstrator BRE.D1

3.2.1 ZEBRA Battery System (h/w component)

One major goal of the charging site CS#3 is to showcase the positive effect that 2nd-life automotive batteries can provide in a stationary buffer storage system, if used in combination with PV and with optional overnight recharging from the grid. For the initial version of the charging station, used (2nd-life) batteries were extracted from decommissioned “Think-City” EVs.

The “Think-City” EVs were equipped with a “ZEBRA” type high-temperature, molten-salt, Na/NiCl battery, manufactured by the Swiss FIAMM SoNick company. ZEBRA batteries do not show any electric self-discharge effects. However, an electrolyte temperature of at least 240°C is needed during operation.

The inevitable heat losses require a continuous supply of thermal energy, which is provided automatically by the battery itself via direct Joule heating.

From five “Think-City” EVs, the respective ZEBRA batteries were physically removed and tested under laboratory conditions. Just two of them passed all tests and were found operational and suited for the demonstration purpose. The remaining three batteries are faulty and cannot be used for this project.

Table 5: Overview of the second-life batteries extracted from EVs

EV	Battery status	faulty cells	Comment	2 nd -life usability
Think-City #1 (generation 0)	partially operational	20	many faulty cells in a single string causes internal balancing currents; no charging without overriding the safety systems	not usable
Think-City #2 (generation 0)	internal electrical insulation error	4	emergency shutdown by the BMS due to internal insulation error	not usable
Think-City #3 (generation 2)	operational	0	battery system (cells + containment + management) fully operational	perfect
Think-City #4 (generation 2)	Cascade failure, battery molten	0	battery containment meltdown during pilot operation	not usable
Think-City #5 (generation 2)	thermal insulation error	0	increased thermal losses; extra heating needed degrading the system efficiency massively	usable
Stationary Battery #6	BMI fault	N/A	battery management interface defective	not usable

Disassembling, transportation and installation within the demo-site were difficult to implement due to large system dimensions and weight (ca. 300 kg) – batteries from EVs are not (yet) designed for a swift relocation within a second-life use case. These activities took much more effort than expected.

Figure 5: Extraction of the ZEBRA battery system from decommissioned Think-City EV

Figure 6: Transportation of the 300kg battery systems to CS#3

3.2.2 PV Inverter (h/w component)

A standard 3.3 kW solar inverter is used to convert the fluctuating DC voltage of the photovoltaic panels into a stable 230V AC sine wave. Built-in maximum-power-point-(MPP)-tracking feature is used to maximize the performance, i.e., the electric energy output. Before data collection can start, a new Modbus RS485 interface module has to be installed and tested.

Figure 7: SMA SunnyBoy single phase inverter

3.2.3 PV Panels (hardware component)

No adaptations were required for usage in pilot operation. The PV panels are in good condition and produce still high enough PV energy.

3.2.4 Battery Inverters (h/w component)

The battery inverters are converting the 300...400V DC output of the stationary buffer batteries into a 230V AC sine wave, which feeds directly into one phase of the power grid. Each battery is connected to its own inverter in order to control the exported energy for each phase separately.

Although originally 3 inverters had been installed, just 2 of them can be used here due to limited amount of operational batteries.

For data collection, a new Modbus RS485 interface modules still needs to be installed and tested, since the original system did not use any control path (Bluetooth was used for configuration).

Figure 8: SMA WindyBoy (for batteries) and SunnyBoy (for PV) inverters feeding into 3-phase system

3.2.5 Battery Chargers (h/w component)

To recharge the batteries from the photovoltaic system, each battery is equipped with a 3.3kW AC charger (BRUSA NLG513). It can also access the public power-grid for conventional charging (needed, e.g., during peak-load situations, for testing purpose, or for simulations).

3.2.6 Smart Meters (h/w component)

The technology prototype CS#3 has been equipped with state-of-the-art smart meters enabling a detailed collection of all electrical parameters for each individual phase of each individual charge-point. These smart-meters will also be added to the derived technology prototype CS#1 (CS#5).

The smart meters are capable of collecting and recording the following data:

- Per-phase voltage/current/power factor
- Per-phase power consumption (energy import and export)
- Total power consumption (energy import and export)
- Industry standard Modbus-RTU via RS485 interface
- Live data acquisition with < 1 sec time resolution
- 40A/phase current limit.

Figure 9: Bi-directional smart meter installed for each charging socket on CS#3

3.2.7 Wallbox Prototype (h/w component)

Both charging-points of CS#3 are equipped with re-engineered wallboxes, which were previously used as stand-alone charging stations. Within the first project phase all planned actions have been completed.

The following adaptations and modifications of the wallbox OEM version had to be made in order to meet the project requirements:

- Standard power meter is removed
- Embedded PC is removed
- Power supply is replaced
- Connections are replaced with 22kW capable cables
- External control interface/bus connection is added
- Electrical insulation distances are improved.

After rebuilding, all required tests were passed, including:

- Test of the IEC 62196 (Type 2 Mode 3) compatibility
- Charge system test using real EVs
- Electrical insulation tests
- Visual inspection
- Bus system test
- Control path test (smart charging)

Figure 10: Wallbox prototypes installed on CS#3

Figure 11: Wallbox prototypes during laboratory testing

3.2.8 gridctrl.ENCORE (s/w component)

This software component is briefly described in D4.3/D.4.4. Since it is a proprietary component, it can be described here just regarding its overall functionality.

The gridctrl.ENCORE is a new development that is under construction throughout the whole project. In its first (initial) version v1.0, although being implemented it will be able to extract some but not all of the data needed for KPI calculation.

The ENCORE backend still needs adjustments in the course of phase 1 comprising the following steps:

- Implement gridctrl.cacp protocol (required to connect to the aggregator instances)
- Added redundant, distributed database storage backend.

3.2.9 gridctrl.aggregator (consists of h/w and s/w component)

This software component is also briefly described in D4.3/D.4.4. Since it is a proprietary component, too, it can be described here regarding its overall functionality only.

Figure 12: gridctrl.aggregator as the central management component of CS#3

The gridctrl.aggregator appliance consists of a standard industrial embedded-PC build for harsh environment conditions (extended temperature range, passive cooling) with additional interfaces. These are needed to get access to different bus-systems, e.g. the CAN-Bus used to control the battery systems or the MODBUS used to access the smart meters. A linux based, hardened, in-memory operating system is used for ensuring its reliability.

Figure 13: gridctrl.aggregator operating system tests

3.2.10 Data storage system

The real-time data feeds are stored on a cloud instance of MariaDB (an open source SQL-database) using a distributed storage system as persistent media. This setup can be scaled up to a total of 10TB storage space for each instance. Should the storage requirements increase during pilot operation, then the table space can be distributed over multiple instances. All software components used for this system are open-source and need just a basic configuration. The cloud computing instances are provided by a German hosting provider which complies with all terms of the GDPR.

3.3 Installation and configuration of the demonstrator

The described setup of 4 charging stations enables to compare the respective suitability (in accordance with the project goals) of off-the-shelf components (employed in CS#2 and CS#4) and those components used in a derived technology (CS#1 - resp. CS#5) and/or a customized specific prototype (CS#3).

3.3.1 Technology prototype CS#3

Setting: limited-access company-owned station including PV device (4.7 kWp) and 2nd-life battery storage (“carport”).

Status: Full rework/re-engineering of the existing system accomplished: new charging points, smart meters have been added and tested; The initial version of this site is fully operational.

Figure 14: Prototypes installed on CS#3

All systems are inter-connected via a core 400V AC bus (3-phase) to transfer electric energy between the system modules, the EVs, and the public power-grid. This grid-led approach provides a maximum system stability, since both the solar and the battery system act as secondary components supporting the charging process. Should these components fail or be taken out of service (e.g., during maintenance), a basic charging service can still be provided for the users. This is important, since in the end the users must be confident and satisfied with this combined charging system.

The following block diagram shows the connection between the 4 main components in CS#3:

- Charge-points (red)
- Battery systems (green)
- Photovoltaic system (red - in bottom part)
- Energy/system management via gridctrl.aggregator (dark grey).

Figure 15: System architecture of the carport station (CS#3) comprising wallboxes, PV panels, inverters and stationary 2nd life batteries - operated via the ENCORE backend

Charge Points

Each charge point consists of a type-2 socket and a standard charge controller combined to an advanced smart meter. Both of them are controllable via a dedicated RS485 bus system using a well-documented protocol.

Battery systems

Each 2nd-life battery has its own charger and inverter, which are connected to a single phase of the power grid. This setup allows to control the exported energy with a high resolution. It is primarily used to compensate asymmetric EV loads. Many cars are using just 1 or 2 phases for charging, which inevitably causes unbalanced power consumption. This adverse effect is tackled with the employed setup.

Photovoltaic system

The photovoltaic system provides a peak power of 4.7 kW and is connected to a 3.3 kW inverter. The energy export as well as additional parameters can be controlled via a RS485 Modbus interface. Currently it is pushing all available energy into the local power-grid, since in the initial version the power control functionality is not needed yet.

A full rebuild of the electrical distribution panel inside the carport station (CS#3) was necessary to integrate the new charge-points as well as the additional measurement and data-logging equipment. The main AC bus system is designed for a maximum load of 45 kW – large enough to allow optional extensions of the charging site. Additional electrical security measures, like residual-current circuit breaker, selective fuses and high-current switch disconnectors are in place for safety issues that might occur during maintenance operations.

The 1st iteration phase of the rebuild/integration has been completed and all tests were successfully executed, including:

- Test of the IEC 62196 (Type 2 Mode 3) compatibility
- Charge system test using real EVs
- Electrical insulation tests
- Smart meter data aggregation
- Visual inspection
- Optical fiber link (for fast internet connection).

For the 2nd iteration phase, the full integration of the buffer battery system including the advanced energy management is projected.

Figure 16: Phase 1 of rebuilding the electrical distribution system on CS#3

3.3.2 Derived technology prototype CS#5

Setting: a limited access, company-owned charging station located next to CS#3 (50m).

Status: Enhanced version is operational using readily available components.

Figure 17: EV recharging on CS#05 using off-the-shelf configuration

Figure 18: Architecture of the charging station CS#5 (carport)

3.3.3 Derived technology prototype CS#1 (decommissioned)

Setting: a limited access, company-owned charging station in a parking garage (“Parkallee” site).

Status: Stock version is operational using readily available components and software; upgrade with new components developed for CS#3 is still pending.

Figure 19: Electric car recharging on CS#1 using off-the-shelf configuration

Figure 20: Architecture of the charging station CS#1 (underground parking garage, “Parkallee”)

3.3.4 Off-the-shelf charging station CS#2

Setting: A privately-operated station situated on student apartment ground (“Galileo”).

Status: The station is not operational yet due to contractual issues with the real estate owner that have come up unexpectedly during the project; accordingly, the station has been tested / integrated under laboratory conditions only; hardware will therefore be physically moved to the CS#3 site, thus providing an additional charging point at that particular station but still employing the same backend (gridctrl).

Figure 21: Electric car re-charging at CS#2

A standard OCPP 1.6 interface via mobile network is used to connect the charging station with the backend system. Simple authorization management (RFID card), charging session logging as well as load control are supported.

Figure 22: Architecture of the charging station CS#2 ("Galileo")

3.3.5 Off-the-shelf fast-charging station CS#4

Setting: a privately-operated ac/dc fast-charger with a 43kW-ac output and a 44kW-dc output (CCS + CHAdeMO connector).

Status: This station is fully operational using the stock configuration. However, installation of additional data collection equipment has proven impossible during the project due to serious EMI issues occurring inside the station housing.

Figure 23: Electric car recharging on CS#4

A standard OCPP 1.5 interface via mobile network is used to connect the charging station with the backend system. Only simple authorization management (via RFID card) and charging session logging are supported. Additional functionalities are not available, since only very limited data access is granted from the installed proprietary firmware.

Figure 24: Outline of the combined ac/dc fast-charging station CS#4

3.4 Full test for the demonstrator

As a result of the development phase, the demonstrator BRE.D1 employs 2 advanced charging stations basically, both equipped with a unique backend system that has been (and is still being) modified to meet all the project requirements. Combined with PV energy supply and a stationary buffer battery system, the two use cases defined in D2.9 will be tested.

Now, having its initial version (v1.0) implemented, the BRE.D1 demonstrator is ready for data collection. Currently we expect a short “pre-phase” period for the collection of baseline data. The exact details on how baseline data are collected can be found in a later deliverable (D5.4).

The two additional charging stations CS#4 and CS#2 fitted with off-the-shelf components are fully and partially operational, respectively. Unfortunately, these stations provide just a very limited set of data consisting of session-loggings together with records of the total amount of energy provided during a charging session. Installation of additional equipment for data collection proved impractical due to restrictions from proprietary architecture and due to severe EMI (electromagnetic interference) issues arising inside the fast-charger's housing. Thus, no external sensors or dataloggers could be integrated in CS#4. As a conclusion, CS#4 will not be followed up in this project as part of D1.

Summarizing, nearly all components (hardware and software) have been integrated and tested in BRE.D1 and are ready for operation. The only remaining issue is the stationary battery in CS#03, which still needs to be integrated in the full system.

4 eCar Sharing demonstrator BRE.D2

4.1 Overall Architecture and components involved

BRE.D2 has two different eCar-Sharing demonstrator sites delivering relevant research data to the project on two eCar-Sharing stations, where the components described in D4.1 are installed to demonstrate the following 2 use cases as defined in D2.9:

- On UC#3, ZET is providing an exclusive Car Sharing solution for residents together with local housing developers. In total ZET is handling up to 4 different housing stations across the city of Bremen. All stations are accessible for the public, residents are receiving a special discount. ZET is gathering data to analyze, whether opening the charging points to the public would constitute a business case.
- On UC#4, ZET is developing a solution to provide public transport data to their Car Sharing users. We believe that the future of a mobility solution is an intermodal system. This development will increase the user experience to a new level. ZET is gathering data to analyze, how this development fosters the usage of public transport.

BRE.D2 consists of one core system and two additions. The core system includes the In-Vehicle-System, the fleet management system and a customer car sharing frontend (CS-Frontend). Supplementing the core system with an interface for the local public transport system constitutes part of the CS#6 pilot site (see Section 4.2.4). The plan of installing a “Smart-Charge”- Backend changed, so this component was replaced.

Figure 25: Architecture of demonstrator BRE.D2 ("eCar Sharing in a residential neighbourhood")

4.2 Adaptions done for the eCar-Sharing demonstrator

4.2.1 CS-Frontend - ZET APP (s/w component)

ZET has developed within the GreenCharge Project a new car-sharing App. This customer frontend is the core part of the ZET Car Sharing service and allows the user to easily book an EV, open and lock the vehicle keylessly, to pay for the ride, and to get information about traffic and public transport.

The new application combines information from different system components and delivers an optimized output to the customer. Through the combination of information from the newly developed Fleet management system and the optimized In-vehicle system, the ZET App is able to provide:

- Optimized smartphone access to eCar sharing service;
- Relevant vehicle status information (e.g. SoC and estimated range);
- Multi modal route planning (including real-time traffic and public transport data);
- Open API documentation for an easy onboarding of additional services.

Figure 26: Screenshot CS frontend (ZET App)

4.2.2 Fleet management system (s/w component)

The self-developed fleet management system replaces the GTS fleet management software. The new system was necessary for the integration of the new service components. The fleet management backend is sending data between the in-vehicle-system (OTA-Key) and the user interface (CS-frontend).

This backend is also used by the fleet manager to overview maintain the running service. The system provides detailed information about user profiles, bookings, and payments to ensure fast and overall user support. It also enables the Fleet manager to request several nearly real-time EV status information. Especially the geolocation (GPS) and the current state of charge (SoC) are important for the management of an eCar-sharing service.

4.2.3 In-vehicle system (h/w component)

The EV-Fleet is running in daily business in several spots all over Bremen. The replaced *miveo*-in-vehicle-system is still serving as a backup system, while OTA-Key is providing main service functionality. There are two main advantages to this change:

- 1) The OTA-Key Box system plugged to the EV’s OBD2, transfers more relevant information to the fleet management system:
 - Vehicle-ID
 - State of Charge (SoC)
 - Charging Started/Ended
 - Estimation of km-range
 - Geolocation
 - Driving patterns.
- 2) Due to the installation of the circuit board inside of the OTA-Key Box, an RFID-interface within the vehicle is not needed anymore. The ZET app creates a virtual key for every booking. When the booking starts, a Bluetooth connection between the ZET app - installed on the customers' smartphone - and the OTA-Key box enables the opening and locking of the booked EV. The mechanical key is no longer part of the customer journey, which will probably improve the customer’s experience and minimize the maintenance effort.

4.2.4 Charging Stations (h/w component)

Due to business reasons two of our sides had to be changed. The public EV-Sharing stations KISSINGER and RICARDA-HUCH (mentioned in D2.10 *Implementation Plan for the Bremen Pilot*) are replaced by two other equivalent charging stations.

Table 6: Charging stations for eCar-Sharing

#	Status	Type	name/location	charger	power limit	Employed in Use case
#5	inactive	public	KISSINGER Kissinger-Str./Utbremer Ring	22kWac / type 2 / mode 3	22 kW	#4
#6	inactive	public	RICARDA-HUCH Ricarda-Huch-Str.	22kWac / type 2 / mode 3	22 kW	#3
#5	active	public	LESUM PARK Charlotte-Wolf-Allee	EVE Single Pro-line system (Alfen)	12,7 kW	#4
#6	active	public	EURO Europahafen	EVLink Smart WallBox system (Schneider)	22 kW	#3

An RFID-interface is still the only opportunity to access the charging station. It is not possible to connect the existing charging infrastructure to the ZET Application so far. The main reasons for this are unforeseen contractual issues with the housing association owning the charging infrastructure.

Regarding the research data collection, there is no need for a “SmartCharge” backend, since the in-vehicle-system in itself provides the required charging data. The only relevant information of such a backend would have been the time-stamps (charging start/end). Since the OTA Key Box sends this information as well, this solution allows an optimized return of investment.

The number of charging stations in the BRE.D2 demonstrator will expand in the near future . For an optimized on-boarding, ZET will use the outcome of the evaluation of UC#3 and UC#4 results.

4.3 Installation and configuration of the demonstrator

4.3.1 Overview installation roadmap

The OTA-Key box needed a connection with the fleet management software and the CS-frontend developed by ZET. The following table provides an overview of the installation roadmap. It should be noted that meanwhile all the components needed for the demonstrator and mentioned in table 7 have been installed and tested successfully.

Table 7: List of implementation issues - dates and testing results

Testing	Date	Description	Status
Installation of test-vehicle key in OTA- Key Box	10.05.2019	EV-key sent to OTA-Key. Incorporation, installation, and registration of EV- key.	success.
Installation OTA-Key to EV (Nissan-Leaf)	15.05.2019	First connection of OTA Key Box to EV by OBD2.	success.
Connection of OTA-Key Box and backend-system	15.05.2019	First connection of OTA-Key Box and CS-System. Testing of key functionality.	failed; adaption needed.
Connection of OTA-Key Box and CS-System (2)	20.05.2019	Connecting OTA-Key Box and CS-System. Testing of key functionality	success
Send and receive data to/from EV	31.05.2019	Connection of OTA-Key Box and CS-System	success
Installation of all vehicle keys in OTA- Key Boxes	03.06-24.06.2019	Vehicle keys send to OTA-Key. Incorporation, installation and registration of vehicle keys.	success
Re-equipment of EV-fleet	29.06.-05.07	Connecting OTA Key Box to vehicle by OBD2.	delayed
Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and backend-system	08.07.2019	Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and CS-System. Testing of key functionality and dataflow	3 error reports. adaption needed
Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and backend-system (2)	12.07.2019	Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and CS-System. Testing of key functionality and dataflow	2 error reports. adaption needed
Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and backend-system (3)	20.07.2019	Connection of OTA-Key Boxes and CS-System. Testing of key functionality and dataflow	success
Connection Frontend to OTA-Key.	12.08.2019	Testing of booking via Application	failed. adaption needed
Connection Frontend to OTA-Key (2)	19.08.2019	Testing of booking via Application	registration failed; database error

Connection Frontend to OTA-Key (3)	09.09.2019	Testing of booking via Application	success.
Implantation of public transport live data	30.09.2019	Testing the availability of live data	success.
(Internal) User experience	01.10.2019-31.10.2019	Testing of usability in real live scenarios	success.
Real-time dataflow	12.11.2019	Testing of real-time dataflow according to GreenCharge requirements	success.

4.3.2 Vehicle key installation

The installation of the vehicle key within the OTA-Key Box requires the expansion of the circuit board out of the mechanical EV Key. An OTA-Key plug soldered to the key circuit board enables the control of the opening and locking function.

Figure 27: Soldered OTA-Key plug

By plugging the soldered EV Key into the OTA-Key box, this component is ready for installation in an EV.

Figure 28: Installed vehicle key

4.3.3 In-vehicle system installation

The in-vehicle installation is simply done through plugging the OTA Key Box to the EV's OBD2 slot.

Figure 29: OTA-Key box installation

4.3.4 Connection to software environment

The integration of the OTA-Key box into the software environment encompasses the connection to both the CS frontend and the fleet management system. Main installation problems had appeared during this integration into the ZET software environment.

OTA-Key provides a software development kit (SKD) to implement the box in different software solutions. The used car-sharing system was built around a few interfaces by using the provided software library. More details are given in D4.3.

Especially the connection between the OTA-Key system and the backend-system (fleet management system) has caused time delays. Finally, just a firmware update on the OTA-Key box enabled such a connection. Therefore, the firmware of all installed boxes had to be updated - bluetooth-enabled via a smartphone.

Enabling data flow requires a registration of the inserted SIM-card in the fleet management system following the completed update of the OTA-Key box. In the test result, the fleet management system should show all required vehicle information – in particular the geolocation data.

Through the connection of the in-vehicle system and the fleet management system, it is possible to authorize potential App users to open and lock the vehicle via a Bluetooth connection. The testing phase ensured the key functionality of the booking process.

Figure 30: Screenshot of firmware interface

Figure 31: Screenshot of SIM registration

4.4 Full test for the demonstrator BRE.D2

4.4.1 Connection of in-vehicle- and fleet management system

As described in section 4.3, one of the main issues according to the installation and configuration of the pilot is the connection between the OTA-Key in-vehicle system and the fleet management backend system. The OTA-Key box sends multiple data to the backend, which allows the management and maintenance of the EV fleet.

Figure 32: Screenshot fleet management system

The fleet management system provides a detailed overview of management relevant vehicle data like e.g. the geolocation of the vehicle or the nearly real-time energy level. As figure 32 shows, the connection test between the in-vehicle system and fleet management system succeeded. All OTA Key boxes within the EVs are delivering data to the fleet management system.

4.4.2 Connection of fleet management system and CS-frontend

The fleet management system is the link between all system components. The fleet management system uses the data delivered by the in-vehicle system to provide information about booking opportunities to the CS-frontend and in this way to the customer.

If an EV ready for a booking, it appears on the interactive map within the ZET application. With a click on the icon, a customer can book the chosen vehicle.

Figure 30 shows that the connection between all system components is working. The OTA-Key box is sending vehicle information (in this case the geolocation) to the fleet management system. The fleet management system is double-checking the booking status of the vehicle. If the vehicle is ready for a booking, the CS frontend displays the geolocation.

Within an internal user experience testing, ZET members were using the new application to book and use EVs. The following key functionalities were successfully tested:

- The accuracy of geolocation
- The correctness of SoC / Estimation of km-range
- Booking functionalities
- Opening/locking of EVs
- Charging started/ended notification
- Activation of immobilizer following the booking.

Figure 33: Interactive map for booking of vehicle

4.4.3 Registration, booking and payment

The new CS-frontend makes it much easier for the customer to sign in for the car sharing service. According to the German law, a car sharing provider needs to check license of a customer and save a copy of it. The new App allows the customer to take a photo of its driving license and upload it directly, so the registration is done within minutes. In this step, the customer also needs to choose the preferred payment method. Payment can be done by credit card or PayPal.

The functionality and user-friendliness were part of the testing phase. The following issues were of particular interest:

- Registration possible with complete dates only;
- Registration possible with driving license only;
- Registration possible with a valid credit card only;
- Booking is correctly billed;
- Receiving billing email.

Figure 34: Screenshot of registration interface

4.4.4 Results of GreenCharge Project Phase 1 (BRE.D2)

The following Table 8 summarises the improvements made so far in the course of the GreenCharge Project:

Table 8: GreenCharge improvement overview

Element	Before GreenCharge	After GreenCharge Phase 1
CS-frontend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before GreenCharge, the only way to book an EV was to book it via the Move-About website. This website was not optimized for usage on a mobile device, which led to poor user experience; • Website maintenance and updating were only possible via a thirty party, which led to a lack of flexibility and higher costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZET APP is customized to be used via mobile devices and is available for android and iOS; • The microservice-oriented ZET App is very flexible improving maintenance issues and allowing modifications to be implemented quickly; • The ZET App provides users with traffic information and public transport data;
Fleet management system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GTS fleet management system was able to provide information about bookings, payments, and vehicle location; • Information about relevant vehicle status data (e.g. state of charge) was not delivered; • No automatic billing system included. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZET fleet management system • Provides information regarding bookings, payments, and geolocation of vehicle; • Delivers data about vehicle status (including SoC); • Provides an automatic billing system.
In-Vehicle system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Miveo in-vehicle system delivered data about the vehicle; • The installation required a car mechanic and produced a downtime of 1 to 3 days. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The OTA-Key Box is sending more detailed relevant vehicle data to the fleet management system; • Following the implementation into the ZET software environment, the OTA-Key box can be installed within minutes

5 Conclusions and Further Work

5.1 eRoaming BRE.D1

In the BRE.D1 demonstrator, currently no eRoaming system has been implemented yet. However, as stated in D4.3: “As a prospective extension within the project, the Hsubject HBS eRoaming system can be integrated to enable temporary access to the corporate charging infrastructure to visitors without the requirement of dedicated charging-vouchers or guest accounts”.

Following this optional feature, in the figure below a proposal is shown on the interaction of components that need to be customized in order to enable eRoaming. This procedure would affect primarily the gridctrl charge management system.

Figure 35: Components involved in a prospective eRoaming approach

5.2 GreenCharge@work demonstrator BRE.D1

The development and engineering of the 2nd-life battery storage system (that forms an integral part of charging station CS#3) has taken (and still takes) substantially more effort than was initially projected. On the other hand, the CS#3 site now constitutes the core element of this demonstrator. Using this charging environment, innovative technologies can be tested to reduce grid power usage and optimize self-consumption in the context of EV charging with renewable energy sources. Therefore, project activities have been focused onto this particular site, since its fully customized hardware allows significantly enhanced data recording capabilities.

Further work on the BRE.D1 demonstrator will now focus on CS#1 (relocated and renamed as CS#5) and the optional usage of hardware and solutions into the carport station CS#3. It is obvious that commercial charging stations can still be used to test technical solutions for derived technologies.

The other two charging stations (CS#2 “Galileo” and CS#4 dc/ac semifast charger) are employing off-the-shelf components. They turned out to be of very limited use regarding data acquisition. This appears to be a general problem that all commercial charging stations would encounter, if it comes to specific data acquisition needs. Despite these limitations encountered in the course of the project (see 3.3 above), lessons learned were quite useful. It was shown that these off-the-shelf components cannot be customized or enhanced in a straightforward manner. As a consequence, just a very limited data-set can be provided from these stations. Such charging stations are restricted by the OCCP 1.5/1.6 standard protocol, which does not allow for, e.g., retrieving data on the SoC from the dc fast charger. It therefore does not fulfill the data-recording requirements for the project and a “green-charging”-effect cannot be investigated. These stations had therefore to be abandoned with respect to project results and evaluation – but remain relevant for the positive user experience. To that end, CS#4 will continue to be operated using off-the-shelf components, whereas CS#2 will be physically relocated to provide an additional charging point at CS#3.

5.3 eRoaming BRE.D2

In the BRE.D2 demonstrator, no eRoaming system is implemented, since this would require extensive development of new hardware and software components. Special costly hardware is required that would allow sharing a charger, while the car-sharing vehicle is still in use. Currently, the car-sharing vehicles at ZET are not used frequently enough to constitute a prospective business case for ZET via implementation of an eRoaming system in BRE.D2.

5.4 eCar-Sharing demonstrator BRE.D2

The launch of the ZET car-sharing application will change the user experience and fleet management. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the newly created processes over the next period. The business model evaluation will use customer interviews to identify potential, to improve the customer experience, and to unravel further needs of the ZET Application. Meanwhile, an internal process will evaluate the way of managing the fleet, the processing of the payment, and the new way of customer service via the ZET Application.

The learnings of this evaluation will improve the eCar Sharing service. The results will show which further developments are needed to fulfill user needs. D2.14 *Intermodal On-street Car Sharing Stations in New Housing Development* will catch up these learnings and will show, how ZET use them to extend the demonstrator. The next generation car-sharing service probably will be more intermodal, rise the usage of EVs as well as public transport, and have a significant impact on emissions inside cities.

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